

CORDEX-FPSCONV errata report

This report was generated automatically on 2025-04-28 17:36 UTC from the "Errata"-labeled issues opened in the CORDEX-FPSCONV github repository, which can be found at <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/cordex-fps-conv/issues>. Please, check there for further detail on the issues and potential new known errors in the data.

Date	Issue (with link to details)	Variables	Model	Experiment	Status
2025-03-03	Wrong names for relative humidity on pressure levels in CLMcom-ETH simulations	hurs200, hurs500, hurs700, hurs850, hurs925, hurs1000	COSMO-crCLIM	All	OPEN
2025-04-25	GHG concentrations in CNRM-AROME do not completely follow the RCP8.5 scenario	All	CNRM-AROME41t1	All	Won't fix